

FOOD AND FEEDING HABITS OF *Synodontis batensoda* IN LAKE GBEDIKERE, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The food and feeding adaptations of *Synodontis batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State Nigeria were studied. Fish samples were collected from July to December 2008; the stomach contents were analyzed using frequency of occurrence method. The fish is an omnivore, feeding mainly on plant parts (25.06%), fish parts (10.09%), insect part (9.8%), crustaceans (9.91%), mollusk (10.1%) detritus (10.49%) and sand particles (16.8%), unidentified particles (7.75%). The length-weight relationship implied that adult male fish had the highest standard length (23.9cm) followed by the adult female (22.5cm) and the juveniles (9.0cm).

KEYWORDS: *Synodontis batensoda*, stomach content, feeding adaptations, Gbedikere Lake.

INTRODUCTION

The fish family Mochokidae is presented mainly by genus *Synodontis* commonly known as catfish. Reed *et al*, (1967) described twenty *Synodontis* species found in Northern Nigeria, while Holden and Reed (1972) indicated that at least twenty one species have been identified in the Niger. The different *Synodontis* species vary in commercial status in different locations, many are important food fishes and some have attractive hues and exhibit behavioral characteristics that make them potential ornamental candidates.

Synodontis accounts for important parts of the commercial catches in Northern Nigeria and, according to Reed *et al* (1967), they are available throughout the year. In the River Niger, *Synodontis* accounted for 18.00% by number and 18.68% by weight of the total fish caught (Mortwani and Kanwai 1970). Reed *et al*, (1967) reported some natural food substance of some common *Synodontis* species. The food and feeding habits of ten species captured in River Niger have been investigated (Imevbore and Bakare, 1970). Olatunde (1979) conducted similar studies on *Synodontis schall* in Zaria, Nigeria.

Synodontis batensoda are found through out Africa, except in the Southernmost parts of Magreb, although most species occur in Central and West Africa, the species occur throughout most of the freshwaters of the Sub-Saharan Africa and the Nile River (Friel and Vigliotta, 2006). The state of knowledge on the various *Synodontis* species in Nigeria is largely on their gross anatomy and some behavioural characteristics. The available scientific investigations on their biology are still inadequate for their propagation and management. This study examines the food and feeding habits of *S. batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Lake Gbedikere is a natural lake located between Latitudes 3^o24⁰ and Longitudes 5^o14^E and is about 10km to the East of Oguma the Head quarter of Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Water enters the Lake from tributaries that run from River Benue during rainy or flood season. When the season is over, the Lake separates out. The Lake is about 450m north of Gbedikere village. The water body covers about 400 – 450m and a depth of 10 – 14m deep, depending on the season.

The Lake is used for fishing and other domestic activities; consequently most of the settlers around the Lake are fishermen (Upper Benue River Basin Development Authority, 1985). The lake experience two seasonal periods; the rainy season starts in the month of May and last till October and is characterized by heavy down pour which sometimes have an extensive flood action. The dry season is from late October to April and is characterized by cold,

dusty -dry wind followed by intense heat. The lake contains fish, other aquatic animals and some macrophytes such as wire grass (*Cyperus articulatus*) which are used for waving mats.

COLLECTION OF SAMPLES

Samples of *S. batensoda* were identified and collected from the fishermen catches using gill nets and Malian traps between July and December 2007. A total of sixty specimens (60) were examined. The total length (TL, cm) of each sample was measured.

The gut of the fish was removed by making a longitudinal incision along the mid ventral line form the mouth to the anus to expose the visceral organs. The gut was removed carefully by detaching it from other internal organs and fatty tissues. The gut length (GL) was then measured to the nearest cm on a graduated measuring board. The stomach was cut off from the gut and weighed on an electric top-loading balance (Satorious) to obtain the stomach weight (SW). The stomachs were scored 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100% according to its fullness as described by Olatunde (1978).

Fig 1: Length-weight relationship of male *Synodontis batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State.

Table 1: the mean of the stomach fullness condition of *Synodontis* Lake Gbedikere, Bassa, Kogi State.

Sex	N	0/4	4/4	¾	½	¼	Subtotal	Percentage (%) total
AF	34	0.32	0.38	1.06	0.72	0.44	2.93	28.26
AM	47	0.23	0.28	0.77	0.53	0.32	2.13	20.62
JV	19	0.58	0.62	1.89	0.79	0.79	5.26	50.92
Grand total	100	1.13	1.34	3.72	1.55	1.55	10.33	100

AF = Adult female, AM = Adult male, JV = Juveniles, 0/4 = Empty stomach, 4/4 = Full stomach, ¾ = Three quarter full stomach, ½ = Half full stomach, ¼ = One-quarter full stomach.

IDENTIFICATION OF STOMACH CONTENTS

Each stomach was split open and the contents emptied into a Petri-dish. The contents were then observed under a monocular microscope. The food materials were identified with the aid of keys provided by Needham and Needham (1962) and Mellanby (1975).

ANALYSIS OF STOMACH CONTENTS

The stomach contents were analyzed by frequency of occurrence method as described by Hynes, (1950). Each food item was identified and number of stomachs in which each food occurred was counted and expressed as a

percentage of stomach containing food. The method showed the proportion of individuals eating a particular food item in a species. The occurrence of each food item was expressed as a percentage of all stomach with food. That is,

$$P = (b/a) \times 100$$

Where, a = Total number of fish examined with food in the stomach; b = Number of fish containing a particular food item; P = Percentage of occurrence of each food item.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The relationship between the fish TL and GL was computed using a linear regression model

$$GL = a + b TL$$

Where GL is Gut length (cm); TL is Fish total length (cm); a is Constant; b is Exponent.

Fig 2: Length-weight relationship of female *Synodontis batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State.

Table 2: The mean of the food items of *Synodontis batensoda* Lake Gbedikere, Bassa, Kogi State.

FOOD ITEMS	AM	AF	JV	SUBTOTAL	TOTAL %
Plant part	0.1178	0.0852	0.0476	0.2506	25.06
Insect part	0.0465	0.0366	0.0189	0.0189	9.89
Fish part	0.0471	0.0343	0.0192	0.1001	10.09
Crustaceans	0.0465	0.0337	0.0189	0.0991	9.91
Mollusk	0.0475	0.0343	0.0192	0.101	10.1
Detritus	0.0493	0.0357	0.0199	0.1049	10.49
Sand particles	0.0798	0.0577	0.0321	0.1687	16.87
Unidentified particles	0.0356	0.0257	0.0144	0.0757	7.57
Grand total	0.04704	0.3402	0.1901	0.9998	100

RESULTS

FOOD CONTENTS

Analysis of the fullness of the stomach shows that juveniles had highest stomach content 5.26 (50.92%) followed by adult female and male 2.79 (28.26%) and 22.29 (20.82%) respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: The mean of the stomach fullness condition of *Synodontis batensoda* Lake Gbedikere is a natural lake located between Latitudes 3⁰24⁰ and Longitudes 5⁰14^E and is about 10km to the East of Oguma the Head quarter of Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State.

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The percentage of the stomach with food items examined includes; plant parts 25.06%, insect parts 9.8%, fish part 10.9%, crustaceans 9.91%, mollusk 10.1%, detritus 10.49%, sand particles 16.87% and unidentified particles 7.57% (Table 2).

Fig 3: Length-weight relationship of combined sexes of *Synodontis batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake. Bassa. Kogi State.

Table 3: Length and weight frequency distribution in *Synodontis resupinatus* in Lake Gbedikere, Bassa, Kogi Sate.

Sex	Standard length (cm)				Total weight (g)		
	n	Min	Max	Mean ± S.D	Min	Max	Mean ± S.D
Males	47	9.4	23.9	12.9±3.69	14.9	327.5	16.7 ± 69.9
Females	34	9.3	22.5	11.9 ± 2.86	14.3	284.9	53.9± 49.6
Combined sexes	81	9.3	23.9	12.5 ± 3.38	14.3	327.5	62.7 ± 62.27
Juveniles	19	6.4	9.0	7.8 ± 0.84	8.9	14.8	11.6 ± 26.09

n = Number, Min = Minimum, Max = Maximum, S.D = Standard deviation.

Plant had the highest frequency in juvenile similar to the result obtained by Owolabi (2005) in Jebba Lake, Nigeria. It also agrees with Laleye *et al* (2006) in Queme River, Benin, this indicate that *Synodontis* is a omnivorous fish during rainy season even at its offset, followed by sand grain and this, aid them in digestion of hard food like plants. This also shows the species under study is a benthic fish.

Length and weight frequency distribution of *Synodontis batensoda* is shown in Table 3. The standard length (cm) and the weight (cm) for adult male, adult female, combined sex and juveniles were 9.4cm – 23.9cm/14.9 – 327.5g, 9.8cm – 22.5cm/14.3 – 274.9g, 9.3cm – 23.9cm/14.3 – 327.5g and 6.4cm – 9.0cm/8.9 – 14.8g respectively.

The males length-weight relationship is express by the regression equation $\text{Log TW} = 0.0121 + 3.2707 \text{ Log TL}$ ($r = 0.9540$) as shown in figure 1.

The females' length-weight relationship is expressed by the regression equation $\text{Log TW} = 0.0229 + 3.05 \text{ Log TL}$ ($r = 0.9266$) as shown in figure 2.

The combined sexes' length-weight relationship is expressed by the regression equation $\text{Log TW} = 0.0159 + 3.1758 \text{ Log TL}$ ($r = 0.9437$) as shown in figure 3.

The juveniles' length Lot $\text{TW} = 1.1759 + 1.112 \text{ Log TL}$ ($r = 0.7341$) as shown in figure 4.

Fig 4: Length-weight relationship of juvenile *Synodontis batensoda* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State.

Table 4: The mean relative condition factor (K) of *Synodontis batensoda* in Lake Gbedikere, Bassa, Kogi State.

Sex	Min	Max	Condition factor Mean \pm SD
Male	1.34	4.73	2.48 \pm 0.69
Female	1.14	3.99	2.68 \pm 0.62
Combined sex	1.14	4.73	2.56 \pm 0.67
Juvenile	1.53	3.60	2.53 \pm 0.57

S.D. = Standard Deviation, Min =Minimum, Max = Maximum.

The relative condition factor (K) of *Synodontis batensoda* is shown in Table 4. The minimum condition factor (K) is 0.57 while maximum is 0.69.

DISCUSSION

The value obtained showed that males were significantly larger than the females ($P < 0.05$). The b-value obtained during the study was: 3.2707, 3.050, 3.1758, 1.1120 for adult male, females, combined sexes and the juveniles respectively. The b-value recorded indicates that the males, females and juveniles exhibited negative allometric growth based on Tesch, (1968) criteria of 3. Similarly, Pauly, (1984) report that a slope value greater than 3 denotes positive allometric growth, this shows that *S. batensoda* did not obey the cube law of growth (Le Cren, 1951) which is not commonly obeyed by most fishes.

The length-weight relationship also had a value of 0.0121, 0.0229, 0.0159 and 1.1759 for males, females, combined sexes and juveniles respectively. This shows that the rate of increase in body length is not proportional to the increase in body weight.

Lagler, (1952) reported that the "K" values of fish can be influenced by sex difference, age changes in season and gonad maturity. The result of the mean condition factor value showed that the male had higher condition factor compared with females. This could be due to inadequate breeding and spawning pressure. The frequency distribution pattern showed that the specimens examined were made up of more than one age group for males and female.

The analysis of the stomach content revealed that *S. batensoda* are omnivorous utilizing a lot of food items ranging from insect to bottom deposits and vegetable matter, also they are bottom feeders with its mouth suitable for its feeding ability. Most of their diet is usually mixed with mud and sand particles which aids in the digestion of hard food like plants. This type of feeding habits confirms the work of Olatunde and Moneke (1985) who reported that they are benthic fish.

Insect parts constitute a very rich food protein and also contain large amount of fats Nikolsky, (1963). The plant part provides carbohydrate source of the diet, while the balance of the other food item which are principally proteins. This corroborate with Okechi (1970) who reported that grass seed formed a significant proportion of the diet of certain east and West African species of *Synodontis*. According to Olatunde and Moneki (1985), the seed might be blown by wind or washed into the river by the seasonal flood during the rains.

CONCLUSION

S. batensoda is an omnivore, feeding on diverse plant and animal food substances. However, the juveniles show more indignation towards phytoplankton, diatoms, leaves and insect larvae, while the adults exhibit more versatile and complex feeding habit. This fish explore food items of aquatic and terrestrial origin depending on availability as influenced by season and water hydrology.

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